

PARTHENOS

Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

D7.3 Final Report on Training and Education Activities

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DATE: 15th January 2019

PARTHENOS is a Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission. The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

HORIZON 2020 - INFRADEV-4-2014/2015:

Grant Agreement No. 654119

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and Synergies

FINAL REPORT ON TRAINING AND EDUCATION ACTIVITIES

Deliverable Number D7.3

Dissemination Level PU

Delivery date 15 January 2019

Status Final

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Project Acronym	PARTHENOS
Project Full title	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
Grant Agreement nr.	654119

Deliverable/Document Information

Deliverable nr./title	D7.3
Document title	Final Report on Training and Education Activities
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Dissemination level/distribution	PU

Document History

Version/date	Changes/approval	Author/Approved by
V 0.1 31.10.18	First draft of structure and task distribution submitted for comments and feedback from T.7.2 members	T7.2 members
V 0.8 18.12.18	Second draft (full text) submitted for comments and feedback to all 7.2 members	T7.2 members
V 0.9 07.01.19	Second draft amended following feedback and sent as Prefinal Draft to TCD	Ulrike Wuttke
V 0.95 10.01.2019	Prefinal Draft amended following to Feedback TCD and sent as Final Version to PIN for final formatting	TCD, Ulrike Wuttke
Final 15.01.2019	Final review and formatting.	Sheena Bassett, PIN

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1. Executive Summary

This document is the PARTHENOS deliverable 7.3 ‘Final report on training and education activities’ (D7.3). It reports the results of the joint efforts of the PARTHENOS Task 7.2 members from the Fachhochschule Potsdam (FHP, University of Applied Sciences Potsdam, 7.2 Task Lead), Trinity College Dublin (TCD, WP7 Lead), CLARIN (University of Leipzig), the Koninklijke Nederlandse Academie van Wetenschappen (KNAW-NIOD), and Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR) for Phase 2 of PARTHENOS Training. The work has been led by FHP.

The document reports about the implementation of the initial education and training plan carried out in Task 7.2 in the second period and the final adjustments to the education and training plan. It is produced by FHP (Task 7.2 Leader)¹. It is based on D7.1 ‘Initial Training Plan’² and D7.2 ‘Report on training and education activities and updated planning’³ as well as changes that have organically developed during the implementation of the Training Plan in Phase 2.

The document is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** forms the introduction that summarizes the main aspects and outputs of the ‘Initial Training Plan’ (D7.1) and ‘Report on training and education activities and updated planning’ (D7.2). It contains brief background information about the training plan development in Phase 1 (year one and two) and ensuing updates.
- **Section 3** presents the implementation of Phase 2 of PARTHENOS Training and the development of key outputs, including the PARTHENOS Training Website modules, workshops, and the PARTHENOS eHumanities and eHeritage Series.
- **Section 4** is dedicated to the modes of delivery.
- **Section 5** describes the aspects availability and sustainability of the PARTHENOS Training materials.
- **Section 6** contains a list of abbreviations.

¹ PARTHENOS SEP (internal Grant Proposal Document, 2014), p. 49.

² http://www.parthenos-project.eu/Download/Deliverables/D7.1_Initial_Training_Plan.pdf, all URLs in this document were checked on 17th December 2018.

³ http://www.parthenos-project.eu/Download/Deliverables/D7.2_Training_Plan_FINAL.pdf.

2. Background

2.1. Summary Initial Training Plan

The 'Initial Training Plan' (PARTHENOS D7.1) was published in June 2016. It was developed in close cooperation with PARTHENOS WP2 (Community involvement and requirements, see PARTHENOS D2.1).⁴ It contains information about common issues across the PARTHENOS partners related to training within an eHumanities context. The 'Initial Training Plan' provides background information about the PARTHENOS Training overarching principles for the development of the Training Plan, as well as more detailed information about target groups (researchers, cultural heritage practitioners, developers and technicians, managers and policy makers), teaching contents and modes of delivery.

The four overarching principles that were identified for the development of PARTHENOS Training are:

1. "The PARTHENOS Training Plan is targeted at users of digital humanities research infrastructure.
2. The PARTHENOS Training Plan will address two levels of user need: the 'need to know about' (awareness raising) and the 'need to know how to do' (skills building).
3. Although PARTHENOS is a research infrastructure project, we must conceive of our training interventions as relevant far more broadly than to researchers only.
4. Given the resource restrictions within the project, PARTHENOS will focus on asynchronous delivery, 'train the trainers' approaches and partnerships with other projects and initiatives to attain maximum impact." (D7.1, p. 3)

The initial training plan foresaw two phases for the actual implementation. During Phase 1, the focus was to be on more generic levels of information (macro level with a focus on creating general knowledge, skills, and abilities) and during Phase 2 content development would move on to more specialized areas, especially highlighting output and products of PARTHENOS Work Packages. The main modes of delivery were to be through printed materials, the implementation of structured web-based modules and curricula on the Internet and by partnering with other projects. Phase 1 was to be concluded with an

⁴ http://www.parthenos-project.eu/Download/Deliverables/D2.1_User-requirements-report-v2.pdf.

evaluation of trials of modules during face to face training and an assessment conducted by WP2 (see D2.2⁵), with the results of these activities directly feeding into the deliverable ‘Report on training and education activities and updated planning’ (D7.2) and to a presentation at DH Benelux 2017⁶.

2.2. Results Phase 1

Phase 1 module development concentrated on topics at a macro level, focusing on the creation of general knowledge, skills, and abilities that foster an understanding of what Research Infrastructures do in general, the benefits they can create for the respective target groups and what kind of knowledge is needed to successfully engage and work with them. According to these aims during Phase 1, the following modules were developed: “Introduction to Research Infrastructures”, “Management Challenges in Research Infrastructures” and “Collaborations within Research Infrastructures”. These modules were delivered in the form of the online PARTHENOS Training Suite⁷ that was developed together with WP8 and launched in February 2017⁸. The modules contain various materials (website texts, slides, lectures, short explanatory videos, further learning, etc.) to cater to different learning approaches. The materials can be studied independently or integrated into other contexts, e.g. by instructors looking to add content to their courses. Training materials developed by PARTHENOS Training were successfully used for training events during Phase 1, especially through partnering with other projects. A highlight was the one-week PARTHENOS Workshop during the ESU 2016 at Leipzig⁹, which was received very positively.

Additionally, a printed brochure for policy makers (‘Why Invest in Humanities Research Infrastructures’)¹⁰, was delivered, targeted at an audience that is tasked with making decisions about investments in research infrastructures.

⁵ http://www.parthenos-project.eu/Download/Deliverables/D2.2_Report_Assessment_Education_Training.pdf.

⁶ Jennifer Edmond, Vicky Garnett, Soft Skills in Hard Places: the changing face of DH training in European research infrastructures, 2017. Pre-print as presented at the DH Benelux Conference, 2017: <http://www.tara.tcd.ie/handle/2262/85444>.

⁷ <http://training.parthenos-project.eu/>.

⁸ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/introducing-parthenos-training-suite> - accessed 10th January 2019.

⁹ http://www.culingtec.uni-leipzig.de/ESU_C_T/node/655.

¹⁰ http://www.parthenos-project.eu/Download/20161123_policymakers_leaflet_share.pdf.

2.3. Assessment and Updates after Phase 1

The methodology and results of the assessment of the 'Initial Training Plan' by PARTHENOS WP2 are described in detail in D2.2 and D7.2.

The following points summarize the main findings:

- The “Train the Trainer” approach is especially useful as it creates a network for reuse and dissemination.
- Some concerns about the accessibility of the asynchronous training programs and sustainability after the end of PARTHENOS were raised.
- Career stages (early, mid, advanced) were not considered as relevant for the level of experience related to Research Infrastructures.
- The suggestion to aim for clearer descriptions of target groups and audiences and to consider archivists as a separate group. Maybe split technical developers into two groups (advanced development and enduring service).
- Content: The most important topics are data sharing, knowledge creation, and sustainability; these topics are well reflected. More focus on how to promote the life cycle of engagement in Research Infrastructures in general is needed, as well as hands on sessions, and linking theoretical work with existing projects.

An overview of the relevant feedback from both the external expert reviewers and the internal PARTHENOS Work Package reviews can be found in D7.2 (p. 22).

3. Implementation of the Training Plan in Phase 2

Based on the assessment of the 'Initial Training Plan' and further discussions within WP7 and within the PARTHENOS WP Steering Committee, five guiding principles for PARTHENOS Training were adopted in Phase 2 with the following as primary focus points:

- Sharpen modes of delivery and focus more on user needs.
- Broaden focus to learning through research infrastructures (not only about them).
- Expose the knowledge developed within the PARTHENOS WPs to a wider audience.
- Expose the knowledge developed within the PARTHENOS Cluster Partners with a special focus on CLARIN and E-RIHS.
- Explore synergies between the goals of tasks 7.2, 7.3, and 7.4 with a special focus on creating a wider audience for the PARTHENOS materials and new forms of training.

With the results of the assessment of the 'Initial Training Plan' and the results of the discussion of the PARTHENOS WP Steering Committee, it was planned for Phase 2 that subject specific content for the PARTHENOS Training Suite would be developed around the knowledge of the respective PARTHENOS Work Packages and Cluster Partners. This input could take form either as full separate modules or submodules, but also as stand-alone additional materials (such as videos or case studies). Additional to actions outlined in D7.2, WP7 would actively seek out further opportunities for collaboration with internal and external partners.

For Phase 1, the creation of content was mainly in the hands of the PARTHENOS Training team. While involving colleagues from other PARTHENOS WPs as broadly as possible, WP7 members produced most of the materials. For Phase 2 the strategy was different. It was foreseen that the process of integrating requirements and outputs from the individual PARTHENOS WPs and partners would require more consultation and input from colleagues from outside WP7. It was foreseen to manage the risk inherent in this strategy opportunistically (i.e. by capturing material at events and presentations being planned for

other purposes) and by making participation and contribution to WP7 activities as easy and enriching as possible for our partners.

Task 7.3 (Coordination and assessment of Trans National Access, led by NIOD-KNAW) analysed the way Transnational Access was provided to project users, how it was received and whether there were lessons to draw from that; both for Research Infrastructures and for policy makers (results of this work are published in D7.4 'Report on the assessment of Transnational Access activities in participating projects'). The five research infrastructures which informed this task were: CENDARI, an RI integrating digital archives for the Medieval and World War One eras; ARIADNE¹¹, an RI for archaeology¹²; IPERION-CH¹³, an RI for heritage science; EHRI¹⁴, an RI supporting Holocaust researchers and CLARIN-ERIC¹⁵, an RI built around digital language resources.

Since the start of the task, crosslinks were investigated, analysing whether the outcomes of the task were suitable to base Training Materials around. However, in contrast to other modules in the Training Suite, Transnational Access was considered a niche subject, for which the potential audience would be relatively small. As the potential of the task lies in influencing policy-making, a more worthwhile way to progress would be to explore other platforms to disseminate the results and brainstorm on the future of TNA in European Framework Programmes.

Task 7.4 (Definition of higher education curricula, led by TCD) was charged with investigating the state of Research Infrastructure integration into current Higher Education training across Europe. In addition to this, T7.4 also integrated some of the PARTHENOS Training Materials developed in Tasks 7.1 (led by TCD) and 7.2 (led by FHP) into a Higher Education programme. This was implemented through a newly formed module at King's College London. This course was delivered from October to December 2018 and students evaluated the training materials through an online survey. The results of the evaluation of this module are to be published in D7.5 (forthcoming).

¹¹ <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/About>.

¹² <http://www.iperionch.eu/>.

¹³ <http://www.iperionch.eu/>.

¹⁴ <https://ehri-project.eu/>.

¹⁵ <https://www.clarin.eu/>.

3.1. Guidelines Phase 2: Training Goals and Focus Areas

For the roadmap for the daily work of PARTHENOS Training for Phase 2, WP7 translated the five guiding points above into five focus areas:

- Increase WP representation.
- Increase Cluster Partner representation.
- Use face-to-face events to evaluate training with end-users.
- Improve the current Training Suite and materials.
- Promote PARTHENOS Training work.

3.1.1. Increase WP Representation

WP2 (led by CLARIN) acts as a cross-link between all PARTHENOS WPs. One of its main tasks was the collection of user requirements for all PARTHENOS WPs to start their work and then later in the project to assess different project products. While WP2 is crucial to the overall development of PARTHENOS, it itself does not produce its own services or tools. Following an initial consultation with WP2 members, it was proposed that training materials could be developed that focused on the writing of use cases for research purposes. This outcome was reconsidered in Phase 2. Because it was expected that such material would be only of interest for a rather limited audience (those who are directly involved in infrastructure building) a different approach was developed by WP7 together with the WP2 lead and CLARIN representatives that would appeal to a broader audience. It was decided to develop training materials that would be especially suitable for supporting researchers to use tools and resources provided by research infrastructures for their research, in particular large, rich social and cultural data sets, thereby broadening the user base for such resources and promoting innovative and sustainable research methods. This led to cooperation on a new Training Suite module dedicated to “Digital Humanities Research Questions and Methods” and the new “PARTHENOS eHumanities and eHeritage Webinar Series” (see below).

Both training interventions met the Phase 2 goal of approaching training needs with a stronger focus on the researcher’s perspective, thus enabling them to learn *through* research infrastructures and to learn how research infrastructures empower their research

in different research contexts. The new module was designed to provide an umbrella for several distinctive submodules that would each highlight different collections of source materials and relevant tools, thus appealing to different groups of audiences, while underlining the common value of digital approaches. The outline of the module and its two initial submodules (“Collections of Parliamentary Records” and “Collections of Computer-Mediated Communication”) were developed by CLARIN and feature several CLARIN resources and tools. The new module will be released at the end of January 2019 and can be accessed from the Training Suite Module overview¹⁶. From the outset this module was intended to be open for the integration of additional submodules, developed either by CLARIN itself or by other partners (from inside of PARTHENOS or beyond) to represent a variety of research contexts and digital methods and tools, thereby offering a platform to interested external parties to utilize the infrastructure built by PARTHENOS Training and to draw from our experiences in producing new educational materials. During Phase 2 of the project, negotiations were started with E-RIHS¹⁷ for a submodule around medieval sources and the Impresso project¹⁸ around collections of newspapers, which will be delivered by the end of the PARTHENOS project.

WP3 (lead by KNAW) works on policies and implementation strategies concerning data management, an area where training is clearly required as has been highlighted by an expeditionary survey conducted by PARTHENOS.¹⁹ Around one hundred responses were received from researchers both within and external to the PARTHENOS community. This research, which focused on the FAIR Principles and EOSC concept, has been conducted as a collaboration between several PARTHENOS WPs led by the project coordinator Franco Niccolucci with WP7 being actively involved. Therefore, in January 2018, a new module entitled “Manage, Improve and Open Up Your Research Data” was published, with heavy representation of the issues being tackled by WP3. This includes data management issues such as standardisation, open access and open data, data management planning, and managing cultural heritage assets. The module was written largely by WP7 members, in collaboration with members from WP3, and also included external contributions from Europeana.

¹⁶ <http://training.parthenos-project.eu/training-modules/>

¹⁷ <http://www.e-rihs.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://impresso-project.ch/>

¹⁹ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/the-fair-principles-and-the-eosc-concept-in-parthenos-community>

WP3 also contributed to the “PARTHENOS eHumanities and eHeritage Webinar Series” (see below), with the resulting webinar having been integrated into the module “Manage, Improve and Open Up Your Research Data”. Additional training activities are foreseen around the launch of new WP3 products (such as the print material that is being produced related to the PARTHENOS Data Management Guidelines with its focus on the FAIR Principles, the PARTHENOS Wizard, and the PARTHENOS Data Management Planning tool). These additional activities can only be discussed in more detail with WP3 representatives once the new products are released.

Last but not least, we established cooperation with the Open Library of Humanities (OLH)²⁰ to produce a short video contribution around the topic of Open Access, especially from the perspective of libraries and that will probably be of specific interest for Cultural Heritage Institution (CHI) practitioners, a target group we committed to specifically address. This video was released in December 2018, as a use case within the context of the module “Manage, Improve and Open Up Your Research Data”.²¹

WP4 (led by INRIA) is dedicated to issues like the advantages of common standards and at the heart of its works is the Standardization Survival Kit (SSK)²², which was launched in October 2018.²³ Standards were already well represented in the Phase 1 modules and are also prominent in the Phase 2 module “Manage, Improve and Open Up Your Research Data”. WP4 also contributed to the “PARTHENOS eHumanities and eHeritage Webinar Series” (see below), with the resulting webinar having been integrated into the aforementioned module “Manage, Improve and Open Up Your Research Data”.

Intense consultation with WP4 representatives, e.g. at the SSK Workshop hosted by INRIA at Paris in May 2018 where several 7.2 task members were present to discuss educational perspectives around the SSK²⁴, led to the conclusion that instead of developing a whole module around standards (which would double the content of the SSK), our strategy would be to highlight en route the importance of standards throughout the Training Suite by integrating the SSK widely into the existing structure of the Training Suite. Some examples of our activities related to WP4 are given in the following paragraph.

²⁰ <https://www.openlibhums.org/>.

²¹ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/parthenos-presents-interview-eve>.

²² <https://ssk-application.parthenos.d4science.org/ssk/#/>.

²³ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/standardization-survival-kit-1-0-launches-today>.

²⁴ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/ssk20>.

As part of WP4 activities, a brochure with two characters, Mork and Tork who were specifically designed to be aliens and, therefore, neutral with respect to nationality, discipline or gender, was produced to introduce people to the notion of Data Standards. To increase the outreach of this brochure, WP7 worked with WP4 to produce a video version of the printed comic. The finished version included sound effects and voice-over work by PARTHENOS project members. Given the nature of the illustrations, we were able to straightforwardly produce the video in different languages versions. The text was therefore translated by PARTHENOS project members from English into French, Italian, and German, and were voiced by the same members from each of the respective countries. These were published via YouTube in April 2018. In November 2018, a Greek version was also produced and published via YouTube. The videos now form an integral part of the “Manage, Improve and Open up Your Research Data” module.

Task 7.2 is also actively liaising with WP4 to identify potential new SSK scenarios that can be developed around new PARTHENOS Training Suite modules and submodules, e.g. around collections of parliamentary records (a submodule within the new module “Digital Humanities Research Questions and methods”).

The scope of **WP5** (led by FORTH) is semantic interoperability. This WP defines a common semantic framework for the technical infrastructure built by PARTHENOS. WP6 (led by CNR) creates the tools and services to enrich and link together digital resources.

In December 2018, the “Formal Ontologies: A Novice’s Guide” module was launched. Mostly project partners from FORTH wrote this module. It also includes contributions from project partners at King’s College London and was edited by project partners from TCD. The module offers a stepping-stone into learning about formal ontologies and what they can do for Humanities data. Topics covered include data heterogeneity and the tools available, including the use of thesauri and authority files to reduce ambiguity in data, semantic data for information management, and an introduction to some of the more common formal ontologies that might be used with Humanities data. It once again made use of video lectures and other short videos to explain concepts. It also included some very simple exercises to allow the student to get to grips with some of the concepts.

PARTHENOS **WP8** (led by KNAW) is dedicated to outreach and dissemination. WP8 is involved in both the development of content for the Training Suite, as well as its dissemination strategy and execution. As communication, dissemination, and outreach are a “management challenge” all research infrastructures are occupied with, WP8 was glad to share its expertise by contributing to the Training Suite on the topic of impact. This was useful as the task leaders and task members in WP8 can not only speak from their experience in communication in PARTHENOS, but also had close ties with – or practical experience from – dissemination efforts in other projects, such as EHRI and ARIADNE.

At the end of Phase 1, members from WP7 and WP8 agreed to cooperate to create a submodule around impact measurement and success criteria that could be integrated into the “Management Challenges for Research Infrastructures” module. After careful consideration, however, this initial plan was slightly adapted to more strongly reflect the researchers’ perspective and the available assets within and outside of PARTHENOS. This led to a two-pronged approach, meaning that aside from the initially planned submodule, an additional impact submodule in the “Introduction to Research Infrastructures” module was developed. As well as informative texts around common issues in research impact from both the researchers and the infrastructure management perspectives, the submodules contain case studies from the PARTHENOS Partner EHRI and several videos featuring international experts as ‘talking heads’ and longer interviews with international experts (collected in special subsections called “Voices from the Community”). Both submodules were launched in April 2018 and disseminated widely.²⁵ Additional material (three video lectures filmed by PARTHENOS during a workshop at the Humboldt University Berlin around impact measurement in the social sciences and humanities) were added to this module in December 2018.²⁶

3.1.2. Increase Cluster Partner Representation

In order to integrate requirements and outputs of specific PARTHENOS cluster partners, we actively consulted with them to recruit additional, relevant input. Through this process, we were able to integrate new material into already existing modules, and/or include the partners directly into the development of new modules and submodules. Here we were

²⁵ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/research-impact-and-impact-of-research-infrastructures/>.

²⁶ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/measuring-change-in-digital-humanities-videos-from-the-workshop-on-impact-factors-and-success-criteria>.

able to profit from the flexibility of the digital environment of our training materials, as the modules, once launched, are still open to additions and edits to ensure that they remain accurate and relevant. A few examples of dedicated cluster partner cooperation are given below.

- OEAW developed a video around stakeholders that was included in the “Manage, Improve and Open Up Your Research Data” module in April 2018.²⁷
- EHRI made contributions (case studies) to the “Impact” sections that were included as part of the “Introduction to Research Infrastructures” and “Management Challenges in Research Infrastructures” modules.
- CLARIN-led WP2 was responsible for the initial framework of the new module “Digital Humanities Research Questions and Methods” and contributed to it two substantial submodules.
- As already outlined above, the new module “Digital Humanities Research Questions and Methods” was intended from the outset to be open for the integration of additional submodules. The PARTHENOS partner E-RIHS took up this opportunity and is currently developing an additional submodule around medieval manuscripts.
- Last, but not least, DARIAH members have largely written a forthcoming module on Citizen Science (due for release in early Spring 2019) as part of their contribution to WP7. The two members of the DARIAH team involved in writing this module have experience of Public History and Open Science, thereby making them ideally placed to deal with issues of public engagement, and accessible science. This module will focus on the challenges of citizen science specifically from the arts and humanities and infrastructural perspectives, the practicalities of citizen science projects such as recruitment, ethical considerations, data management within a large group and how to give credit, as well as offering some examples along the way.

Last but not least, many of the PARTHENOS cluster partners (e.g. CLARIN, INRIA, OEAW, FORTH, CNR) also contributed to the PARTHENOS Webinar Series (see below) that made their experience and contribution to PARTHENOS Training highly visible.

²⁷ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/stakeholders-collaborative-video>.

3.1.3. Use face-to-face events to evaluate training with end-users

During Phase 2, PARTHENOS Training used several occasions to present PARTHENOS Training materials to key audiences and to gather informal feedback. Though the focus during Phase 2 was on virtual events (the “PARTHENOS eHumanities and eHeritage Webinar Series”, see below), several occasions gave us the opportunity to test and validate our knowledge-sharing vehicles and approaches, especially around the new module “Manage, Improve and Open Up Your Research Data”. For example, from the Webinar Series, we received the feedback that humanities specific material related to Citizen Science was considered as a valuable contribution by PARTHENOS, which was taken up by DARIAH in the context of the PARTHENOS Training Suite. From the face-to-face events we learned that the researchers’ interest in topics such as Data Management and Open Science is highly tied to their own gains (“What’s in it for me?”).

Focusing more strongly on incentives, teaching practical skills while promoting available solutions developed and maintained by infrastructures, is the future route to pursue in order to embed and support these highly important topics at the heart of the community. Highlights of the Phase 2 face-to-face events included our continued cooperation with the ESU at Leipzig in 2018²⁸ and an Open Science Workshop at the CARMEN Annual Meeting 2018 at Tampere²⁹, to mention just two.

3.1.4. Improve the current Training Suite and Materials

An online platform such as the PARTHENOS Training Suite is a living structure that needs permanent maintenance. For Phase 2 we set ourselves the aim of broadening the reach of our training materials by offering some materials in languages other than English. While translation of full modules was not feasible given our restricted resources, we had to carefully consider which materials would be the most useful. Expert feedback pointed towards introductory materials for novice audiences and thus we launched a trial with a translation effort for our well received Mork and Tork Cartoon Videos, which were translated from English into several other languages (so far also in French, German, Italian, and Greek).

²⁸ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/parthenos-research-data-teaser-session-at-the-esu-2018-leipzig>

²⁹ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/parthenos-discusses-open-access-at-annual-meeting-for-medievalists-in-tampere>

Figure 1: Result of Brainstorming during WP7 Hackathon at Dublin in November 2018, picture Ulrike Wuttke, CC BY 4.0

Over time, and with multiple editors, a website can develop inconsistencies that need addressing. To address this, we held a half-day ‘Hackathon’ in November 2018 to identify the main areas of inconsistency within the training materials, and agree a uniform approach that produced a template for further module development (see Figure 1).

Unifying this content would also ease the next step in the process, that of migrating the content on the current Training Suite to a new platform (in January 2019). As a result of this migration, certain formatting features and plugins were expected to be lost. Therefore, there was little sense in formatting these. Instead, it was agreed that we would focus on the structure and elements on each page. Implementation of these templates across the Training Suite was conducted throughout November and December 2018.

3.1.5. Promote PARTHENOS Training Work

To make sure that PARTHENOS products and services find their way to their target groups, the PARTHENOS project contains a designated Work Package (WP8) which communicates and disseminates project output. With T7.2’s on-going creation of training material and WP8’s focus on communication, dissemination and outreach, the relationship between this task and this work package has been mutually beneficial. While the on-going creation of new training material frequently provided new reasons for our audience to visit our website, the circulation of this news via various channels attracted a wide interest, which – to give one example – led to all webinars being nearly fully booked (see Table 1).³⁰

³⁰ The upper limit was set at 50 attendees.

Webinar	Registered	Participated
“How to work successfully with eHumanities and eHeritage Research Infrastructures” [1]	49	34
Make it Happen - Carrying out Research and Analysing Data” [2]	34	27
Create Impact with your e-Humanities and e-Heritage Research [3]	55	39
“eHumanities and eHeritage Research Infrastructures: Beyond Tools” [4]	53	34
“Boost your eHumanities and eHeritage research with Research Infrastructures” [5]	44	27
Sum	235	161

Table 1: Registration and attendance PARTHENOS Webinars

Figure 2: Tweet PARTHENOS Webinar Series

PARTHENOS uses several online media channels to communicate about the project and its training materials. New modules are always announced via news articles on our website.³¹ The URL of the article on our website allows for further dissemination via social media (Twitter and Facebook). The tweet around the PARTHENOS Webinar Series³² became the most popular tweet in the 3rd year of the project (see Figure 2).

The #TrainingTuesday hashtag has been introduced to accompany a recurring event on Twitter whereby on a regular basis we create a curated playlist on the PARTHENOS YouTube channel of Training Suite videos focused around a particular topic or announce other new materials.

New modules are also often featured in the PARTHENOS newsletter. Offline, the Training Suite features prominently in our leaflets and posters. Last but not least, we use scientific conferences to share insights gained during our work with the wider community and to promote the PARTHENOS Training materials.

³¹ For an example, see: <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/parthenos-releases-new-training-modules>.

³² https://twitter.com/Parthenos_EU/status/951407550343368704.

4. Delivery of Training in Phase 2

Face-to-face delivery of courses as a form of fully guided learning experience is considered one of the best techniques of training to gain in-depth knowledge. Having said this, there are often circumstances that will prevent our audiences from participating in these kinds of courses (with lack of time and lack of money being the most obvious obstacles). Therefore, WP7 has chosen to focus on online materials. Because one of the most important success criteria for the implementation of the training plan is to enhance (re-)use of the materials produced by PARTHENOS in order to raise awareness about the featured topics and themes, WP7 chose to look out for opportunities to put modules into practice. Also, such occasions would offer the possibility to collect informal feedback that may lead to improvements to existing modules or ideas for new modules.

4.1. Partnering: Cooperation and Events

During the second phase of PARTHENOS we have partnered with diverse partners to test our training materials and to raise the awareness about their thematic scope and availability, along with other PARTHENOS products, such as the SSK.

In July 2018, PARTHENOS returned to the European Summer University in Digital Humanities (ESU), hosted by the University of Leipzig. After the planning of a week-long course on the topic of Research Data Management, we realized that this topic did not fit exactly with the other offered workshops at the ESU, which proved to be a strong competition for students' participation. Therefore, we have decided to offer two Teaser Sessions for our topic, each for 45 minutes.

In the end, both PARTHENOS Teaser Sessions were successful and well-attended. The training resources developed by PARTHENOS were presented to the international and interdisciplinary audience. At the beginning, the participants were invited to put the different steps in the research data lifecycle in the correct order, which produced a lot of discussion and subsequently led to highly interactive sessions (see Figure 3). Apart from the introduction to the basics on Research Data Management, the audience had the

possibility to ask questions and to propose new topics for future webinars in the PARTHENOS Webinar Series.³³

Figure 3: Participants of the ESU 2018 PARTHENOS Teaser Session engage with the Research Data Life Cycle, picture Ulrike Wuttke, licence CC BY 4.0

Due to unforeseen developments, it was not possible to cooperate as planned with the Humanities at Scale (HaS) project to feature the new module “Manage, Improve and Open up your Research Data” in a partnering event. We were, however, able to highlight these materials as well on several occasions at international and local level, such as at the CARMEN Annual meeting 2018³⁴, the Luxembourg Open Science Fair 2018³⁵, and to a group of Early Career Researchers at Potsdam University during summer 2018. We also shared our experiences with starting communities such as ReIRes³⁶, where we presented not only PARTHENOS products and services for the eHumanities and eHeritage Community, especially related to FAIR data, but also our knowledge and experience related to the development of training.³⁷

Whenever appropriate, we would also publish the slides as Open Educational Resources (OER) and promote them in social media to increase the impact. Sometimes, we would also use partnering events to capture new material, such as at the international workshop “Measuring Change in Digital Humanities: Workshop on Impact Factors and Success Criteria” at Humboldt University Berlin³⁸, where we filmed several presentations as additions to the WP8 impact submodules (see above).

³³ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/parthenos-research-data-teaser-session-at-the-esu-2018-leipzig>

³⁴ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/parthenos-discusses-open-access-at-annual-meeting-for-medievalists-in-tampere>

³⁵ <https://openscience2018.uni.lu/programme/#1544186709353-b7664664-41ea>

³⁶ <https://reires.eu/>

³⁷ <https://reires.eu/1899/reires-workshop-in-mainz-on-the-fair-principle-for-digital-research-data-management/31/>

³⁸ https://www.ibi.hu-berlin.de/de/forschung/information_retrieval/projekte-aktivitaeten/workshop-dariah-eu

As is, unfortunately, the case in any project, many promising leads for building training opportunities were also pursued but unable to be brought to completion for reasons unrelated to PARTHENOS. A successful presentation to LIBER in 2016 led to the planning of a follow-up workshop, but the planned event had to be cancelled and postponed indefinitely. Contact with members of the IPERION-CH project was made in the hope of capturing some of their training school events, but this too proved not to be feasible in the end. The work of PARTHENOS was also presented to the IPERION Summer School in 2018³⁹, but this is unlikely to be able to lead to much follow up given the short remaining duration of PARTHENOS.

4.2. The PARTHENOS Webinar Series

While generally being very positive about the development of the PARTHENOS Training Suite and the available resources, the assessment of the Initial Training Plan (D7.1) by WP2 led to the suggestion for Phase 2 to seek novel opportunities for the delivery of training to augment its on-line offerings (D7.2), especially by putting the modules into practice. Given the resource restrictions within the project to offer synchronous on-site training, we opted to seek to fulfil the user requirement for engaging live formats of guided study by organizing webinars, which are interactive, online seminars on the Internet. At the moment, webinars are gaining increasing popularity in various educational contexts and are offered quite regularly as professional development activities by (European) infrastructures and initiatives. As we had learned, at every stage of their professional career, researchers and practitioners alike need to engage in continual professional development to reap the benefits of the ever-changing field of eHumanities and eHeritage research infrastructures (lifelong learning), but often they are not able to spend a lot of time or money for participation in a workshop or summer school. Therefore, we thought it would be worth a try to bring the training live to them, but virtually, on their screen.

As webinars were an addition to the already existing training portfolio of PARTHENOS, we further investigated their specifics, focussing especially on their educational potential and pitfalls and their adequacy for digital humanities and digital cultural heritage methods and tools. After a thorough risk analysis and intensive discussions, especially with WP2 representatives, we decided that webinars have a high potential for knowledge transfer on an introductory level and would be a valuable addition to the existing PARTHENOS

³⁹ <http://www.iperionch.eu/3rd-iperion-ch-doctoral-summer-school/>.

Training portfolio. The webinar approach would lay the focus on a sought after and modern eLearning format and the feedback collected at these events would help to develop further modules. The webinars would also get people to (re-)use the existing modules and raise awareness about the use of digital research infrastructures through all phases of the research process, one of the most important success criteria for the implementation of the training plan.

Figure 4: Research Life Cycle, licence CCO

We set up the PARTHENOS webinars as an introductory training programme with a syllabus that focused on the professional development and capacity building needs and requirements of (digital) humanities and cultural heritage scholars and information specialists related to digital humanities and digital heritage infrastructures. Under the name “PARTHENOS eHumanities and eHeritage Webinar Series” we produced five webinars that covered relevant fields of knowledge and skills that are needed to enhance the awareness and knowledge of using digital infrastructures to assist different phases of the research process. As a discernable educational framework for the series we chose the research life cycle (see Figure 4 “Research Life Cycle”) because its distinctive phases provided a clear user-centric lens and a coherent logical order.

Each webinar was themed around one of the phases of the research life cycle (developing research questions, planning of research, carrying out research, analysing data, and publishing of results) with the exception that we had decided to merge the two most technical phases of the research life cycle (carrying out research & analysing of data) because we considered them to be less suitable and relevant for a novice audience and better replaced with a general introductory webinar. The syllabus was built around use cases with clear relevance for scholars and information professionals. Topics included: theoretical and practical reflections on the role of digital and analogue research infrastructures in Humanities and Cultural Heritage research; opportunities and challenges of eHumanities and eResearch; finding, working with and contributing to digital research infrastructure collections; the role of standards; the FAIR principles and research data

management; ontologies; digital tools and VREs, and, new publication and dissemination types.

During February and April 2018, five one-hour webinars were conducted with international experts from PARTHENOS and beyond and organized by Dr Ulrike Wuttke who also acted as moderator of the series (see Table 2). The webinars were announced with strong support from WP8 via diverse channels, such as the PARTHENOS main site, the PARTHENOS social media channels (Twitter, Facebook), the PARTHENOS newsletter, several mailing lists, and comparable channels of PARTHENOS project partners and other related initiatives.

Create Impact with your eHumanities and eHeritage Research (Research Life Cycle Phase “Publish Results”)
Juliane Stiller (Humboldt-University Berlin) and Klaus Thoden (Max Planck Institute for the History of Science, Berlin)
How to work together successfully with eHumanities and eHeritage research infrastructures: The Devil is in the Details (Research Life Cycle Phase “Plan Research Project”)
Marie Puren (Inria) and Klaus Illmayer (Austrian Academy of Sciences)
eHumanities and eHeritage Research Infrastructures: Beyond Tools (No Research Life Cycle Phase, but General introduction)
Steven Krauwer (CLARIN) and Stefan Schmunk (State and University Library Göttingen)
Make it Happen – Carrying out Research and Analysing Data (Research Life Cycle Phases “Carry out Research & Analyse Data”)
George Bruseker (Foundation for Research and Technology) and Carlo Meghini (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche)
Boost your eHumanities and eHeritage research with Research Infrastructures (Research Life Cycle Phase “Develop research questions”)
Darja Fišer (University of Ljubljana) and Ulrike Wuttke (University of Applied Sciences Potsdam)

Table 2: Overview of the PARTHENOS Webinars

A total of 161 individuals from the eHumanities and eHeritage community with various disciplinary backgrounds and levels or experience (235 registrations) attended the PARTHENOS webinars. All in all, 27 countries were represented, with a peak of 90 participants from Germany, which can be explained by the fact that we used several German mailing lists to promote the webinars. A significant number of participants came also from France (15), the Netherlands (13), the United States (12), Greece (11), Italy (9),

the United Kingdom (9), Ireland (8), Croatia (7), and Austria (7). Besides the United States and Croatia, PARTHENOS has project partners in all these countries, which supported the outreach. Notably, the series reached beyond the European Union (Australia, Cameroon, Canada, Russia, and South Africa).⁴⁰ This success shows its potential for further editions. All webinars were recorded with the intention of including them on the Training Suite.

As PARTHENOS Training aims at producing materials for trainers and for self-learners, we developed a publication and archiving strategy that facilitates the independent uptake and reuse of the webinar materials as Open Educational Resources (OER). More information about the webinars, including learning objectives, full outlines and wrap-ups of the individual webinars that also contain links to the archived webinar materials, such as the recordings and presentation slides can be found in the section dedicated to the eHumanities and eHeritage Webinar Series on the PARTHENOS Training Suite.⁴¹

The PARTHENOS Webinar Series was not only well received, it also inspired WP7 to develop a new module around Citizen Science (see above) because of the interest this topic had sparked. Results and insights were presented during DH Benelux 2018⁴² and an Open Access publication is planned.⁴³

4.3. Uptake

Use statistics provide insight in how successful outreach activities around the Training Suite are. While it's hard to establish a direct link between visitor numbers and, e.g., a tweet or live activity around training, correlations are certainly useful to develop a general feel for what ways of attracting an audience might be successful.

Looking at the development of the use of our Training Suite, it can roughly be divided in two sections: 1st June 2017 – 31st January 2018 and 1st February 2018 – January 2019 (see Figure 5). The graph shows that visitor numbers were around 100 visitors per month in the first period. An interesting outlier shows up around February 2018, when there were nearly 1,000 active monthly visitors.

⁴⁰ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/successful-parthenos-ehumanities-and-eheritage-webinar-series-concluded>.

⁴¹ <http://training.parthenos-project.eu/sample-page/ehumanities-eheritage-webinar-series/>

⁴² Abstract: <http://2018.dhbenelux.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/8/2018/05/DH-Benelux-Submission-PARTHENOS-Webinars-Final-Upload.pdf>, Slides: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1257320>.

⁴³ Wuttke 2019, to appear in Liber Quarterly.

How are your active users trending over time?

Figure 5: Overview of active users over 1. May 2017 until 6. December 2018 (exported from Google Analytics)

There are three potential reasons. Firstly, this is around the period when the Webinar Series was launched. Secondly, the module “Manage, Improve and Open Up Your Research Data” was released on the 29th January. Thirdly, the Training Suite was nominated for the DH Awards 2017⁴⁴ in the category “Best Use DH Public Engagement” around the same time.

After the outlier faded, our audience remained structurally higher, with between 200 and 400 visitors per month. This is promising, as it shows that we managed to retain some of our new visitors. As the webinars remained on-going and new modules are continually added on a rolling basis, this should not be surprising.

What pages do your users visit?

Page	Page Views	Page Value
/	843	\$0.00
/training-modules/	527	\$0.00
/sample-page/intro-to-ri/	308	\$0.00
/for-learners/	202	\$0.00
/sample-page/introduc...arch-infrastructures/	175	\$0.00
/sample-page/management-challenges/	166	\$0.00
/for-trainers/	148	\$0.00
/sample-page/intro-to-r...hat-is-infrastructure/	139	\$0.00
/about-parthenos-training/	111	\$0.00
/test-2/manage-improv...r-research-and-data/	97	\$0.00

Figure 6: Most popular subsites in the Training Suite between 6th December 2017 and 6th December 2018 (exported from Google Analytics)

It is also useful to assess which of the Training Suite webpages are most popular. By looking at the past year (6th December 2017 – 6th of December 2018), we avoid a bias towards the “older” sections, while we still have a significant amount of data to work with. The data shows that our introductory content is still popular (see Figure 6). This goes, for instance, for our “Introduction to Research Infrastructures” page, as well as the main page regarding “Management Challenges”.

⁴⁴ <http://dhawards.org/dhawards2017/>.

As the “For Learners” and “For Trainers” pages also attract views, we can reasonably assume that this ‘guiding’ information is of value to quite a few visitors.

Top Channels

Figure 7: The spread over the different channels leading visitors to the Training Suite between 6th December 2017 and 6th December 2018 (exported from Google Analytics)

Lastly, it is interesting to analyse how our audience finds its way to the PARTHENOS Training Suite. The distribution amongst the different forms of entering the website is depicted in Figure 7. A significant number of our visitors arrive at the Training Suite directly or via organic search, meaning that they purposefully navigate to the website. The visitors who do not navigate to the Training Suite directly (see Figure 8: source/medium no. 1), or via Google/organic search (see Figure

8: source/medium no. 2) have found us via Twitter, dhawards.org, and via Facebook. Especially the DH Awards website is worth mentioning, as apparently it has been even more successful than one of our social media channels. In comparison, however, it’s worth pointing out that Twitter has been an even more important source of traffic to the Training Suite.

Source/Medium ?	Acquisition		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?
	3,558 % of Total: 100.00% (3,558)	3,528 % of Total: 100.00% (3,528)	6,981 % of Total: 100.00% (6,981)
1. (direct) / (none)	1,970 (53.26%)	1,949 (55.24%)	4,021 (57.60%)
2. google / organic	653 (17.65%)	592 (16.78%)	1,203 (17.23%)
3. t.co / referral	307 (8.30%)	267 (7.57%)	628 (9.00%)
4. dhawards.org / referral	68 (1.84%)	60 (1.70%)	136 (1.95%)
5. m.facebook.com / referral	58 (1.57%)	58 (1.64%)	59 (0.85%)

Figure 8: The five most used channels leading visitors to the Training Suite between 6th December 2017 and 6th December 2018 (exported from Google Analytics)

5. Availability of Materials and Sustainability

5.1. Availability of Materials

5.1.1. General

All materials developed by PARTHENOS are available on the project website.⁴⁵ The PARTHENOS Training materials (especially the multimedia materials) developed by WP7 are hosted on several platforms (PARTHENOS YouTube Channel⁴⁶, PARTHENOS SlideShare⁴⁷, PARTHENOS Training Zenodo Community⁴⁸, PARTHENOS collection in HAL⁴⁹). The central entrance point to the materials developed by PARTHENOS Training (WP7) is the PARTHENOS Training Suite (see Figure 9)⁵⁰ which is also prominently featured as one of the projects flagship results from the PARTHENOS main site (c.f. Figure 10)⁵¹.

Figure 9: PARTHENOS Training Suite (Screenshot of Entrance Page, 17.12.2018)

⁴⁵ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/>.

⁴⁶ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnKJnFo_IFfoAl3VH51t1hw.

⁴⁷ <https://www.slideshare.net/Parthenos/presentations>.

⁴⁸ <https://zenodo.org/communities/parthenos-training/?page=1&size=20>.

⁴⁹ <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/PARTHENOS>.

⁵⁰ <http://training.parthenos-project.eu/>.

⁵¹ <https://www.parthenos-project.eu/portal>.

PARTHENOS Training aims at producing materials for trainers and for self-learners. To facilitate the (re-)use of the materials and enhance their impact, we developed a publication and archiving strategy that facilitates the independent uptake and reuse of the webinar materials as OER.⁵² This means that we aim to publish our materials with an open license (CC-BY), technically barrier-free (e.g. in various formats), and make them widely findable by using various publications channels and adding rich metadata.

5.1.2. Cross-links to other PARTHENOS products

Over its lifetime, PARTHENOS has released a variety of products and services. The Training Suite does not stand on its own, but is embedded in this ecosystem of tools and services, which are all in their own way developed to meet the various, but closely related needs of our stakeholders.

Figure 10: A screenshot of the PARTHENOS Portal, 17.12.2018

The PARTHENOS portal is the central location on the PARTHENOS website to access all PARTHENOS tools and services. Many of the tools serve (or will serve, upon completion), a specific goal. To provide two examples: 1) the SSK, for instance, facilitates learning on which standards can be used in which research scenarios, and 2) the PARTHENOS Policy

⁵² <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/communication-and-information/access-to-knowledge/open-educational-resources/what-are-open-educational-resources-oers/>.

Wizard will show researchers, policy makers and data repositories which policies are relevant for the specific discipline they are working in.

The Training Suite is designed to offer a starting point for novices who wish to learn about Digital Humanities research and RIs. This means that it could serve as an accessible gateway into a more specialised subject. An example of how cross-links between tools are established can be found in the SSK, where users who are new to the subject of standards are directed to the Training Suite (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: A screenshot of the Standardization Survival Kit.
URL: <https://ssk-application.parthenos.d4science.org/ssk/#/>

By establishing such links between tools, the strengths of PARTHENOS' different products and services can reinforce each other.

5.1.3. Synergies between PARTHENOS Training and the PARTHENOS Hub & HaS

In D7.2 it was mentioned that synergies between the Training Suite and two specific other platforms would be examined: 1) the PARTHENOS Hub and, 2) the metablog being developed by the H2020 project Humanities at Scale (HaS). The following paragraphs give a brief overview of the results.

Over the past year, the development of the **PARTHENOS Hub**⁵³ started taking shape. It was envisioned as an open accessible publication and interaction platform for the humanities research communities. It experiments with combining the traditional format of

⁵³ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/portal/the-hub>

publishing in journals with the more dynamic, interactive new media (such as blogs, internet forums and social networks). The PARTHENOS Hub consists of different issues, each dedicated to a specific topic. The Training Suite and the PARTHENOS Hub, however, serve different purposes. The focus of the Training Suite is to provide material, references, best practices, guidelines, teaching tools for different aspects grouped around thematically organised modules (such as an introduction to research infrastructures etc.). The Hub, however, can be used in all steps of the research process to facilitate scholarly discussion (collecting/assessing material, scholarly publishing, interaction, persistent documentation etc.). A possible relation between the two exists where the Hub could play a role as a supporting tool: for publication, communication, interaction, and documentation. So far, there has not been an opportunity to combine the two, while this remains a potential opportunity for the future.

Similarly, the cross-links between the Training Suite and Humanities at Scale's metablog "**OpenMethods**"⁵⁴ have been explored actively. The HaS-project, however, ended in June 2018. While it was worthwhile to discuss the challenges we faced as infrastructures building an environment for knowledge exchange and how we dealt with them, there was no active collaboration between PARTHENOS and HaS at this point. However, if an article of interest is published on the Open Methods metablog that ties in thematically with a module in the Training Suite, we are still eager to make the most out of potential synergies.

5.2. Sustainability

The description of work that set out the initial vision and mission for the PARTHENOS cluster is very clear about how the outcomes of the cluster should be sustained:

"All the above statements about "flagship results" end with the sentence "what will remain": this hints to the sustainability of project outcomes. For PARTHENOS, sustainability is an easy task, because it is guaranteed by the presence of the two ERICs, CLARIN and DARIAH, that will be in charge of receiving and maintaining what PARTHENOS is producing in its lifetime. ERICs are permanent institutions and since they participate in

⁵⁴ <https://openmethods.dariah.eu/>

PARTHENOS with a primary role, they will incorporate the project outcomes in their portfolio of services, tools and knowledge resources.”⁵⁵

In the case of the PARTHENOS Training Suite, one of those “flagship results” mentioned above, preparations for this eventual embedding into the activities of CLARIN and DARIAH began with the launch of the project activities. This has shaped the development of and decision-making about the Training Suite and its contents in a number of ways:

1. In terms of technology, we have chosen to use the most basic, open and accessible platforms we could, essentially deploying an .html framework pulling together assets hosted in platforms chosen at the cluster level for the delivery of media (YouTube, SlideShare, etc.). In this way, we ensured that risks of migration and ‘bit rot’ would be minimised over long term, and that findability was maximised.
2. Training focus areas and materials of the Training Suite have been based on high-level issues rather than specific technologies, in order to ensure they will remain useful and relevant for a longer term.
3. All assets have been collected together within a single portal, rather than across multiple platforms for multiple types of training, and all of these are available for reuse under open licenses (generally a form of CC-BY).
4. Stakeholders and parallel projects have been engaged, through our ERIC cluster ‘parents’ as well as beyond. The Training Suite therefore leaves the protective environment of the PARTHENOS funded activities already aligned with its potential partners and ‘siblings’ for further development.

Above and beyond these specific initiatives and decisions undertaken by the WP7 team, the Training Suite and its assets will also benefit from environmental conditions that are in their favour, but beyond their control. Over the past two years, CLARIN and DARIAH have been working together across a number of activity areas, one of the strongest being training and education. The two ERICs already jointly sponsor one major resource, the CLARIN/DARIAH Course Registry, and this experience has solidified the recognition in each organisation that this is a significant area for collaboration between them.

As a way of extending this work, in the final phase of PARTHENOS, a dedicated resource will be employed to begin the work of mapping the assets around the Training Suite that

⁵⁵ PARTHENOS SEP (internal Grant Proposal Document, 2014), p. 20.

are used and promoted throughout the two organisations, and propose a coordinated and synthetic way of carrying them forward together, and continuing to enrich and align them as a unified resource for the user bases of the two ERICs. In this way the benefits of the cluster project investments for CLARIN and DARIAH, for their users, and indeed for Europe, will be maximised.

6. Abbreviations

ARIADNE	ARIADNE is an infrastructures for the management and integration of archaeological data at a European level
CARMEN	CARMEN is a Worldwide Medieval Network
CENDARI	Collaborative European Digital Research Infrastructure
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institution
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
D (as in D7.2)	Deliverable
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DH	Digital Humanities
EHRI	European Holocaust Research Infrastructure
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ESU	European Summer University in Digital Humanities Leipzig
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FHP	Fachhochschule Potsdam - University of Applied Sciences Potsdam
FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas
HaS	Humanities at Scale
INRIA	French National Institute for computer

	science and applied mathematics
IPERION	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage
NIOD	Nederlands Instituut voor Oorlogs-, holocaust-, en genocidestudies - Institute for War, Holocaust and Genocide Studies
KNAW	Koninklijke Nederlandse Academie van Wetenschappen - Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
OEAW	Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften - Austrian Academy of Sciences
OER	Open Educational Resources
OLH	Open Library of Humanities
RelRes	Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSK	Standardization Survival Kit
T (as in T7.2)	Task
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
TNA	Trans National Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package